

Design and analysis of Geographical aspects using Cannister- Sized Satellite Navigation.

Rudresha S^{1*}, Rajani Kodagali², T V Manohar³, Abhishek Chakraborty⁴, Ganesh M⁵, Ravindra Shivaji Kolhe⁶

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Visvesvaraya College of Engineering, K.R.Circle Bangalore-570001, Karnataka, India.

²Department of Computer Science Engineering, CMR University, Bangalore Karnataka 562149 , India

³Department of Computer Science Engineering, Rajajeswari College of Engineering, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

⁴KwantumG Research Labs Pvt Ltd,Bengaluru-560064.India

⁵Department of Computer Science Engineering, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology,NH-66, Kottara Chowk, Mangaluru – 575006, Karnataka, India

⁶Mechanical Engineering , Sanjivani college of engineering D Y Patil International University Akurdi Pune, India.

Abstract

The paper depicts about an educational project CanSat, whose main goal is to build a Canister-Sized-Satellite with the available resources with Indian manufacturers within a constraint of capital cost. The CanSat payload standard requires investigation to be contained in a launch vehicle with compatibility of fit in a cylindrical body of 0.125 m diameter x 0.310 m height with a launch mass of up to 700 g. We describe process to construct the CanSat mounted on Aluminum chassis. The CanSat was launched by the facilities of ISRO-INSPACE-INDIA by a launch vehicle rocket, which achieved a height of 800m. The mission requirements were to measure physical parameters like temperature, air quality, altitude, humidity, position data, orientation data, battery status and health, barometric pressure, latitude, longitude, power data and system status using mechanical actuators and electronic sensors. Mission states are sent to the ground station right from the satellite with reference level as ground. The real-time data packets are received and decrypted at the ground station and the laptop of the ground station graphically visualizes the data obtained. The flight pattern obtained was limited to a plane that covers area of 25X25 m by help of NAVIC. The paper covers designs as well as the recently tested CanSat.

Keywords: CanSat ; Microcontroller; Sensors; Satellite.

1.Introduction

The design and analysis of satellite was done for upgradation and contribution to satellite technology for various purposes including study of climate conditions, geographic conditions, & changes in weather. But the capital cost for studying & analyzing satellite technology is expensive & students of developing countries like INDIA, can hardly manage it.

CanSat is a remarkable rocket payload that may be used to research satellite and space technologies. CanSat is a small satellite about the size of a canister that contains a number of electronic sensors (BMP180), a parachute system to regulate its rate of fall, and a battery module to power different electronic mountings. It is a framework model of a genuine satellite that is housed within a coke can; it neither leaves the atmosphere nor circles around the globe. It may be launched by a rocket to a height of a few metres (700–800 m), and as it descends, it sends scientific data to a base station. The probe's main responsibility is to transmit and retain data that was gathered by sensors during the mission. All the electronic components utilised in our CanSat are listed in Table 1 [3]. Electronic and aeronautical components make up the developed CanSat. A component of aeronautical design is the descent control system [7]. For the CanSat (can-sized satellite) competition, there are financial, physical, and weight limitations. The following subsystems must be included in a viable satellite design: sensors, a storage module, wireless transmission, control, and optional imaging modules. Among the sensors are those for positioning, latitude, altitude, pressure, temperature, and orientation. Prior to being sent to a ground station for processing, all sensor data must be correctly formatted and recorded on a Micro SD storage card. The simulated satellite also records the separation and keeps doing so until landing. The satellite will be found using the GPS module after landing. A satellite with a buzzer will be located if a GPS device fails. [4].

Table 1. Electronic Components List

The adaptation of new technological developments from one area of satellite

15	Model Name	Quantity	Mass Piece(G)	SOURCE
GNSS	EVE L86-M33 GNSS	1	8 ± 0.2	Datasheet
Radio	XBee S2c	1	60 ± 0.3	Datasheet
Pressure/Altitude Sensor	BMP 180	2	5 ± 0.1	Datasheet
Temperature Sensor	BMP 180	1	5 ± 0.1	Datasheet
Air Quality Control	Robocraze MQ135	1	5 ± 0.2	Datasheet
Pitch and Roll Sensor	MPU6050	1	2 ± 0.1	Datasheet

applications to another is common [1]. When Professor Bob Twiggs originally proposed the idea of nanosatellite projects in 1998, 50 students and faculty members from 12 universities in the USA and Japan convened in Hawaii for the "University Space Systems Symposium" [11]. He proposed putting a structure into orbit that was about the size of a coke can, with a mass of 500 kg and a capacity of around 350 millilitres. Using this idea, they initially intended to launch a satellite bigger than 350 millilitres in volume or three 350 millilitre satellites using a rocket that could lift 1.8 kg and go 4 kilometres. That was a great effort to get the price of space travel down to around \$400 [12]. The flights in 2000 used barometer or differential GPS data for calculations relating to unlocking the landing mechanism, making them a bit more sophisticated. The project became somewhat more challenging with the addition of the Comeback category in 2001, when the satellite had to be directed toward a specific target and this mission was successful. Students from Tohoku University launched the satellite 45 metres from its planned site in 2002. Two CubeSat satellites were sent into orbit by the University of Tokyo in 2003. A little larger, cube-shaped satellite than CanSat is called CubeSat [13]. Complex CanSats with capabilities like fly-back flights [14] or landing on a predetermined location [15], descent controlling [16], and data processing [17] are often built for CanSat contests or higher level training. I'm reminded of Project Prandtl by NASA because of this continuity [18]. CanSat Leader Training Program (CLTP), a new advanced training programme, was run for the first time in Japan in 2011. The goal of this curriculum was to educate students space engineering swiftly [19]. Some UAE students have utilised CanSat to research air pollution [20] For undergraduate students, the concept is

both challenging and highly interesting, and it enhances the way space engineering is taught [8]. In order to provide students practical experience with real-world satellite projects, it is preferable to build a CanSat. They can work on any feature, including integration, mission planning, and CanSat testing. Artificial intelligence solutions provide considerable value extraction from vast data infrastructure as a result of the increasing use of sensors and networked equipment in manufacturing. Decision-making and sustainability in manufacturing may benefit from these techniques. There is a lot of scrap in machining due to improper tool maintenance. In order to identify production trade-offs linked to sustainability and the best machining parameters, this study creates an intelligent (IoT) tool condition monitoring system that keeps track of machine tool state. The optimal operating conditions identified by evolving artificial intelligence (AI) algorithm-based multi-objective optimisation are represented as a Pareto optimum front.[21]. The goal of the current study project was to examine the wear characteristics of an aluminium alloy named Al6061 that was produced using the two-step stir casting method. Adding zircon particles strengthened the alloy. Three different percentages of zircon particles were used: six percent, nine percent, and twelve percent. At a high temperature of 100°C, the wear behaviour of Al6061-Zircon composites was examined using a pin-on-disc wear testing equipment. The design of the tests that had been produced using Taguchi's approach was followed for conducting the trials. L27 Orthogonal array was used to do the data analysis.[22]

2.Problem statement

3.Airframe Design

Aluminum male standoffs and perforated aluminum sheets are used to construct the fuselage. Onboard computers, electronics, and computers make up the fuselage. Batteries and a descent control system are also put within the container. Table 1 illustrates the CanSat's geometric properties. Table 2 provides the weights of the CanSat components. CanSat's overall weight shouldn't be more than 0.700 kg. The Top Stage, First Stage, Second Stage, and Last Stage are the four phases that make up CanSat.

Table 2. Geometric Characteristics Of Cansat.

Component/Assembly	Mass[gm]
Overall CanSat Mass	518.00
Descent System's Total Mass	50.00
Camera System Total Mass	66.54
Electronic System Total Mass	305.00
System Structure Total Mass	41.00

Fig. 1. Total 18 Male standoffs are used in hexagonal shape. Male standoffs are made up of aluminium alloy. Male standoffs have a dimension of 5*5*50 mm. All the Male standoffs are connected to chassis. Total 4 chassis are used

in the payload.

Fig. 2. 1st stage has a total of 5 sensors mounted on it in a systematic way such that : Maximum space is occupied; No overlapping of any sensor ;Proper connection of jumper wires.

Fig. 3. Total length of the chassis is 85 mm and height of 60mm.

4.Electronic System Design

The electrical system is heavily dependant on the programmed. Sensors, receiver-transmitters, and software control processors were developed using the C programming language. The electrical and power system is made up of a wide variety of sensors and other parts [9]. Our CanSat's sensors gather vital information including barometric pressure, temperature, GPS, longitude, latitude, and battery life.

1.1. Sensor subsystem design

Our system of sensing modules includes sensors for temperature, air quality, pressure, elevation, GNSS, pitch and roll, voltage level, and an extra camera module. A number of the sensors, including temperature, pressure, and altitude, are merged into a single sensor or component to lighten and lower the cost of the CanSat.

1.2. Block diagram

The data transferred between pressure, temperature, altitude, acceleration, humidity, coordinate, and other variables contains information. The electrical architecture of these satellites often consists of an RF module, a CPU, GPS, micro servos, and a variety of sensors. The information is also provided to the ground control station via the RF module after being analysed by sensors

depending on the tools and equipment used to execute the task. For complex tasks to be managed in the air, a microprocessor is necessary. The software included inside the microprocessor aids in providing a peek of the processes going on within the satellite [6].

The four steps of CanSat's operating procedures are as follows: The data is processed by the processing unit, which also generates a binary stream that is sent to the transceiver for 10 Hz communication. The first level involves sensor units gathering and addressing relevant data from their immediate physical environment, such as temperature and barometric pressure. The transceiver transmits the data in the 2.4 GHz frequency spectrum at a data rate of 250 KBPS using an antenna.

Fig.4. Block diagram

1.3. Ground control station

GCS is essentially a land-based control station that enables the user to control Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), such as satellites and drones (in our instance), etc. One of the most important aspects of CANSAT is the layout of the ground control station GUI. For this research, a wide range of programming languages and development environments—including MATLAB, Java, and LabView—are examined. Visual Studio was chosen as the foundation for creating the ground station GUI because it is an approachable programming environment [2]. The GCS interface allows the ground station operator to transmit calibration commands for the barometer sensor and roll/pitch angles

(from the pitch sensor). The GCS Operator may also provide a command to set the time. Simulated data file will be loaded. The operator will issue an activation command after broadcasting to activate the simulation mode, at which point the ground station will begin receiving consecutive values from the csv file at a frequency of 1 Hz. The GCS also transmits the order to disable simulation mode.

Fig. 5. Payload FSW state diagram

2. Navigation control algorithm

Two control algorithms were created to safeguard CanSat's orientation. The following describes how flight control orientation works:

- The first and second stage parachutes' system stabilizes the CanSat after it separates from the rocket.
- A mechanical gyroscope is employed to orient CanSat.

Hardware Development

1.4. PCB board

Multiple-storied PCBs must be designed due to a space constraint. A GPS board, sensor board, camera board, and control board were all made as independent PCB's circuit board with the required circuitry, a voltage regulator, a voltage divider, and an Arduino CPU.

A temperature and barometric pressure sensor (BMP180) were put on the sensor board.

Connectors were used to create the connection between the controlling unit and the GPS module.

1.5. Frame and decent control system design.

Aluminum was used in the creation of the hexagonal body, which measures 85 mm by 60 mm by 150 mm. The chassis and male standoff can easily sustain a shock of 30G. In parachute design, a dual deployment system was employed. It was divided into two phases: parachute in two stages: first and second. Rip stop nylon is the material used for the primary parachutes, which are fastened together at the top stage of the frame with the aid of fuse wire. There are a total of four secondary parachutes attached to the frame, each of which is made up of rip stop nylon and has its string fixed at the first and second stage chassis and curled up to the male standoffs of the extreme ends.

JIKOF ig.6 . EPS design

Conclusion

The CanSat was successfully executed. It came with a unique GUI. Indian students may research for a fair price with the help of the CanSat project, and anybody who wants to construct a satellite based on comparable ideas can work on such a version to progress the field. The primary goal was to make it convenient and affordable for Indian students, and it was successful. Future work signify will be creating a cheap long-range RF communication module and a cheap launch rocket so that students may launch from greater heights and gather a broader range of data.

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Credit Author Contributor Roles

Conceptualization, Data curation-**Dr.Rudresha S¹**, Formal analysis- **Rajani Kodagali**

Investigation- **T V Manohar** ,Methodology- **Abhishek Chakraborty**,
Project administration- **Ganesh M**, Resources, Software- **Ravindra Shivaji Kolhe⁶**

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